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Scaled-up microwave assisted batch and flow synthesis, and life cycle assessment of a silica mesoporous material: UVM-7

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The development of scaled-up processes for the synthesis and functionalization of silica material is a key issue for its adoption in various applications. This report introduces innovative batch and flow methodologies for the synthesis and functionalization of substantial quantities of UVM-7, a silica mesoporous material exhibiting a bimodal pore system. The synthesis benefits from the combination of the atrane route with a reduction in reaction time induced by microwaves generated with a solid-state source. To our knowledge, this is the first example of a flow microwave-assisted synthesis of silica mesoporous materials. The materials were characterized by thermogravimetric analysis, X-ray diffraction, transmission electron microscopy and, N₂ absorption /desorption isotherms. The scaled-up procedures, encompassing both batch and flow, are capable of synthesizing as-made material in less than 15 minutes, yielding materials with a topology characteristic of UVM-7 akin to those synthesized via conventional methodologies. The functionalization process can be executed in less than five minutes with loadings of organic moieties of 3.2 mmol of APTES (g of silica)⁻¹. Within an hour, as-made material for more than 150 g of calcined UVM-7 could be synthesized, and up to 60 g can be functionalized. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) using the ReCiPe method indicates that the most significant impacts are in the categories of freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, and human carcinogenic toxicity. The scaled-up synthesis offers a substantial reduction in environmental impact in those categories, a 5-fold reduction in the CO₂ equivalent emissions compared to the non-scaled synthesis and up to half compared to conventional synthesis. The main contributors are solvents in the functionalization and energy consumption during the calcination.

Introduction

Silica mesoporous materials have been widely explored at the research level in recent decades. We can cite as a first example the MCM-41 published in 1992.¹ These materials are characterized by an ordered mesopore system with a pore diameter of around 2 nm. The presence of a pore system with a uniform size distribution and the ease of functionalization with both organic molecules and inorganic oxides or nanoparticles have allowed the development of a wide range of materials with the most diverse applications.² The pore size of MCM-41 limited its application, so other materials with larger pore sizes quickly appeared, such as SBA-15 or SBA-16.³ Among the fields in which silica mesoporous materials have been used we can mention catalysis, biomedicine, sensors, controlled release, etc.⁴ By contrast to MCM-41, that shows a unimodal mesopore system, nanoparticulated silicas can offer a hierarchical bimodal porosity also, and this feature can improve accessibility and mass transfer (in both directions; between the pores and the

outside). For example, UVM-7, prepared through a one pot procedure by using a simple template agent and starting from silicon atrane complexes as inorganic precursors, presents a very open architecture based on a continuous network constructed from covalently bonded pseudo-spherical mesoporous primary nanoparticles whose aggregation defines a nonordered secondary system of large textural pores.⁵ This organization favours the mass-transfer processes inside UVM-7 silicas, which improve their applicability.⁶

The preparation of mesoporous silica materials is mainly based on the sol-gel method in a hydroalcoholic medium, in the presence of a surfactant or polymer. These act as structure directing agents and generate the final material the mesoporous structure. The typical synthesis process for this class of materials comprises synthesis (at room temperature or heating, generally including an aging process), emptying of the pores by calcination or extraction, and a subsequent functionalization process. This method, which we could describe as "conventional", has been complemented with other strategies aimed at obtaining materials more quickly, with higher yield or novel morphologies. Some examples of alternative methodologies use ultrasounds, microwaves, or mechanochemistry.⁷ Among them, microwaves are especially suitable for this purpose since they considerably increase the reaction rate, which means less processing time. In this sense, the authors of the present work reported a microwave-assisted

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UVM-7 synthesis method that allows the use of solid-state microwave generation technology to prepare, calcinate, and functionalize a mesoporous silica material in only 4 hours.⁸ In part, the success of the result is due to the use of solid-state (SS) microwave generators that allow the generation of radiation with a controlled and stable power, even for small powers, and with a narrow range of frequencies.⁹

Compared to other silica materials such as zeolites or fumed silica that are usually prepared in large quantities, mesoporous materials are generally only prepared in batches and at the gram level, limiting their practical application. Thus, the development of synthesis procedures that allow to obtain larger quantities of material is a topic of interest. The scaled-up synthesis methods reported tend to depart from organosilanes or a low-cost source of silica such as sodium silicate or rice husk following the common sol-gel procedures.¹⁰ In other cases, alternative techniques more scalable such as spray drying are applied.¹¹ However, they are limited in general to a few grams, even only 1 gram. Conversely, the gradual injection of reactants has been revealed as an interesting technique for the preparation of dozens of grams of monodisperse microporous silica particles in 3 hours, but unfortunately, the resulting material had a pore diameter narrower than 1 nm.¹² An attempt to use the same technique in presence of surfactant to obtain an ordered big size pore structure, produced only disordered materials with area up to approximately 500 m² g⁻¹.¹³ Remarkably, Zhang et al. were able to obtain up to 1 Kg of spherical silica nanoparticles with stellate, worm-like or raspberry-like morphology departing from TEOS heating the reaction mixture for 2 hours.¹⁴ Going a step further, 1 kilogram of mesoporous silica nanospheres with a surface area of 500 m² g⁻¹ were prepared in absence of organic solvent in 3 hours using a combination of cationic and anionic surfactants.¹⁵ However, none of these examples take advantage of the possibilities that microwaves offer to speed up synthesis.

Another possibility to obtain large amounts of material is the development of flow synthesis strategies. This allows the continuous obtention of materials with homogeneous properties and facilitates automation. However, until now it has generally been limited to microfluidic systems and the use of this approach to obtain silica materials in large quantities has not been reported. A particular case is the use of roll-to-roll fabrication technique coupled with an evaporation induced self-organization for the preparation of ordered mesoporous materials.¹⁶

In the present work, we hypothesize that the use of solid-state microwaves in batch or flow systems may be a good strategy to obtain mesoporous silica, specifically UVM-7, in large quantities while reducing the environmental impact.

Results and discussion

The preparation process of mesoporous silica materials can be divided into two independent stages, (i) the formation of the silica structure, "synthesis" from now on, and (ii) the surface modification with organic silanes, "functionalization" from now

on. In the present work we set ourselves the objective of achieving a scaling factor of 100 in both stages. A first approach to obtain large amounts of material is to continue working in batch but increasing the size of the reactor. This is not immediate since aspects such as the mixture of the reagents, the homogeneity of the reaction, and the transmission of energy can be dependent of the batch size. An alternative approach is the use of flow synthesis, which offers as main advantages maintaining a smaller reactor size and the possibility of automation.

Scalation of the microwave assisted batch synthesis and functionalization.

BATCH SYNTHESIS

Figure 1.a shows a scheme of the synthesis assembly. The power source consists of four 2450 MHz SS microwave generators. The power generated by each of the sources is transferred to the cavity through a coaxial cable connected to an antenna. Thus, the cavity is fed by four antennas. The reaction mixture is placed in a glass container and elevated above the cavity to avoid field decrease in the vicinity of the surface. Following our previous results, as an initial approximation we proposed a scaled synthesis process in which the use of energy was proportional to the amount of water.⁸ Considering that we sought to multiply by 100 the amount of material, that implied a microwave power of 5 KW. This value is much higher than the 800W of combined potency of the four solid state sources. Thus, we increased the irradiation time to 12.5 minutes. This could be also advantageous, since in our previous results a longer irradiation time led to an increase in the volume of inter-particle pores and therefore to the expected diffusion capacity.⁸

As expected, the formation of a white solid in the reactor due to condensation and growth of silica is observed experimentally. The process occurs quickly, in about 10 minutes and is accompanied by a decrease in reflected power. This suggests that the gel formed couples better with the incident

Figure 1: a) Scheme of the batch reactor; b) normalized XRD of the materials BS800 (solid line), BS400 (dashed line) and a conventional synthesis (dotted line); c) Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms of BS800; d) Representative TEM images of BS800.

Table 1. Textural properties of UVM-7 mesoporous materials synthesized or functionalized in this work.

Material	2θ ($^{\circ}$) ^a	Area ^b (m^2g^{-1})	Mesopore volume ^c (cm^3g^{-1})	Mesopore diameter ^c (nm)	Textural diameter ^c (nm)	Textural volume ^c (cm^3g^{-1})
BS800	2.11	956	0.82	2.8	37.2	2.05
BS800c	2.23	801	0.85	2.6	59.9	1.62
BS800s	2.01	1024	0.67	2.6	29.9	0.58
BS400	2.17	937	0.51	2.5	30.7	1.37
BF-4	2.15	372	0.15	2.3	33.6	0.46
FS-1	2.29	928	0.78	2.8	47.8	2.30
FS ^d	2.04	980 ± 50	0.84 ± 0.04	2.82 ± 0.04	34.0 ± 1.8	0.77 ± 0.13
FF ^e	2.01	220 ± 160	0.08 ± 0.04	2.7 ± 0.2	54 ± 4	1.02 ± 0.10
Conven. Synth	2.13	969	0.78	2.7	49.9	1.44
Conven. Func.	2.14	251	0.15	2.6	39.6	0.96

^a Angle of incidence for the reflection plane.

^b BET specific surface calculated from N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms.

^c Pore volumes and pore size(diameter) calculated from N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms.

^d Average and SD of the fractions FS-2 to FS-4.

^e Average and SD of the fractions collected in during the flow functionalization.

radiation than the solution/sol of origin and may be a tool to detect the end point of the reaction. After calcination 35 g of material is obtained, equivalent to a yield of 95%. Nearly all the silicon from TEOS is incorporated into the final material.

The material obtained under these experimental conditions (BS800) presents the typical characteristics of UVM-7. Low angle XRD shows a peak around 2° (2θ) corresponding to the reflection (100) of the hexagonal mesoporous structure. In addition, a wide signal of lower intensity is observed on 3.5–4.0° (2θ) due to the overlapped (110) and (200) reflections of a hexagonal lattice (Figure 1.b). TEM shows the structure of this class of materials consisting of small mesoporous particles that aggregate giving rise to the presence of large textural pores between them (Figure 1.d). This type of morphology is confirmed by the N₂ absorption/desorption analysis, which includes a high surface area, about 956 m² g⁻¹, and a bimodal pore system with two well-differentiated adsorption steps (Figure 1.c, Table 1). The first one, occurring at relatively low relative pressures ($0.2 < P/P_0 < 0.4$) is related to capillary condensation in the 2.8 nm mesopores of the particles. Its shape, sharp and without hysteresis loop, suggests these mesopores are uniform and cylindrical. The second step, occurring at high relative pressures ($P/P_0 > 0.8$), corresponds to the filling of 37.2 nm inter-particle pores formed between primary nanoparticles. If we compare our material with that obtained by conventional synthesis it is observed that in general, it presents the same properties. The UVM-7 prepared following the conventional procedures has larger inter-particle pore, but typically this parameter is one of those that presents greater variation.⁸ This fact opens the possibility to modulate in a finer way the larger pores through a modification of the MW preparative conditions.

Since the reactor has a diameter of 14 cm, one of the aspects that worried us was that inhomogeneities could be generated in the reaction medium. The combination of a short reaction time with the limited penetration capacity of the microwaves could lead to hot and cold spots, with a consequent decrease in the homogeneity of the final product. Thus, a new batch

irradiated at 800W for 12.5 minutes was prepared, and samples were taken from the centre (BS800c) and the side (BS800s) of the reaction flask. Although, in all cases the material can be qualified as UVM-7 (see Table 1 and Figure S1 in the Supplementary material), there is indeed a certain difference between the properties of both samples. The mesopore size in both cases is equal and the BET area, despite its variation, falls into the range of a mesoporous UVM-7 (typically between 800 and 1100 cm³ g⁻¹) (Table 1). Again, the main difference lies in the process of aggregation of the particles to form the large-pore architecture. In any case, it is appropriate to limit the width of the reactor to ensure the homogeneity of UVM-7. Additionally, a longer reaction time was tested (400W and 25 minutes) maintaining the energy input (BS400). Although BS400 is a bimodal mesoporous material, it presents a lower volume of mesopore and slightly reduction in the pore diameter (see Table 1 and Figure S1 in the Supplementary material). Furthermore, only 25 g of material before calcination was obtained, which corresponds to a yield of 68%. It seems that microwave power is not an innocent element and that it has a considerable influence on the kinetics of the hydrolysis and condensation reactions.

The microwave-assisted UVM-7 synthesis process is a widely scalable process. Extrapolating our results and considering our equipment, the proposed synthesis method would allow to prepare material "as made" to obtain more than 150 g of calcined material in just one hour and opens the way to its industrial application.

BATCH FUNCTIONALIZATION

Functionalization is a common process in the preparation of silica nanomaterials. The surface modification allows that the materials act as sensor, controlled release material, etc. In our case, the synthesis equipment and configuration are the same as those used in the synthesis section. Our goal in this case was to achieve a 50-fold scale, without increasing reaction times. To obtain a more sustainable process, as well as to reduce the reaction volume, the concentration of the reactants was tripled. The APTES:UVM-7 ratio remained constant. The power selected

Figure 2: a) Scheme of the batch reactor; Representative TEM images of FS-1 (b), FS-2 (c), FS-3 (e) and FS-4 (f); d) normalized XRD of the materials FS-1 (dashed line), FS-2 to 4 (dotted line), and conventional synthesis (solid line).

was 200 W and diverse times of irradiation (4, 8, 12 and 16 minutes) were executed. With only 4 minutes, TGA revealed that a high degree of functionalization is achieved. 3.2 mmol of APTES (g of silica)⁻¹ were incorporated to the surface of the UVM-7, similar to the 3.6 mmol of APTES (g of silica)⁻¹ that can be obtained by conventional synthesis. An extension of the reaction time to 8, 12 and 16 minutes increases the organic content to 3.3, 3.7 and 4.0 mmol APTES (g of silica)⁻¹ respectively. However, we believe that for most applications the slight increase in load does not justify the need for higher energy and time consumption in this synthesis process. This degree of functionalization is significantly higher than that previously found for microwave functionalization (1.8 mmol) for the same time.⁸ Although we cannot rule out other reasons, we believe that this result could be due to the increase in concentration derived from the reduction in solvent volume. As expected from the functionalization process, chemically mild to silica, the silica structure is not affected (see Table 1 and Figure S1 in the Supplementary material). However the coating of organic matter reduces the size and accessibility of the pores. This effect is more pronounced in the mesopores due to their smaller size leading to a reduction in the total surface of the material to 372 m² g⁻¹ (Table 1). In view of the results, we can conclude that microwave assisted batch functionalization is also a very scalable process and that it can help to considerably reduce reaction times. If we consider that the reaction time is 4 minutes, in 1 hour about 40 grams of the mesoporous material UVM-7 could be functionalized.

Flow microwave assisted synthesis.

Flow synthesis offers an interesting option for the preparation of materials in large quantities due to its versatility and the homogeneity that is conferred to the products. In addition, in the case of microwaves, it allows to avoid the formation of hot and cold spots because the liquid is in motion, and the diameter of the conduction can be adjusted to avoid significant power losses. Unlike batch synthesis, as the dissolution mass is lower, the power requirements are lower. Thus, we work with a source of only 200W and one antenna.

FLOW SYNTHESIS

To carry out the flow synthesis we departed from two solutions, one containing the atrane complex, and the other one the water necessary for hydrolysis and condensation. Both are mixed just before the microwave inlet, within which they are irradiated with the solid-state source. A schematic of the synthesis set can be seen in Figure 2.a. A power of 100 W and a residence time of the solution inside the furnace of 1 minute were established. Samples of the prepared material were collected for 20 minutes in 4 batches to compare the homogeneity throughout the reaction time. As can be seen in Figure 2 and from the data in Table 1, there is an important difference between the material generated in the first 5 minutes (FS-1) and the following fractions. In comparison with the material obtained in the conventional synthesis of UVM-7, the FS-1 fraction presents a certain displacement at larger angle (2.3°) in XRD, indicative of a slightly smaller cell size (Figure 2.d). In addition, TEM shows that FS-1 present a structure of large mesoporous particles surrounded by smaller ones (Figure 2.b). This structure diverges from common UVM-7 composed of aggregated small particles. Probably the reactor has not reached the steady state during

the first minutes, and this fraction should be discarded. The rest of the fractions have the characteristics of UVM-7. Table 1 shows that the textural properties of fractions FS-2 to FS-4 are common for UVM-7, and that the variability throughout the synthesis is relatively small, reinforcing the idea that microwave-assisted flow synthesis may be an appropriate strategy to obtain the material with homogeneous properties. XRD shows that the peak has a slight displacement at a smaller angle (from 2.13° for conventional synthesis to 2.06° for flow synthesis) which corresponds to a slightly larger cell size. Regarding the structure of the particles, TEM shows that in microwave-assisted flow synthesis maintain the UVM-7 structure (Figure 2.c, e and f). The flow synthesis would allow the preparation of 82 g of material after calcination in one hour. This value is lower than the scaled-up synthesis in batch but, in any case, opens the door to an automatic preparation of UVM-7 in large quantities.

FLOW FUNCTIONALIZATION

Finally, we studied the possibility of developing a continuous process for the functionalization step. The functionalization is more complex than the synthesis. The hydrolysis and condensation are processes fundamentally in homogeneous medium. The synthesis parameters were adjusted so that the formation of the material occurred in the final part of the reactor. However, for the functionalization we start from a solid and it is a heterogeneous phase reaction. The configuration of the equipment for functionalization is slightly different from that of the synthesis step. APTES and the material were added directly to the acetonitrile solution, so that only the use of a peristaltic pump was necessary. In addition, it was necessary to make some adaptations to facilitate the transit of the material through conduction. Although acetonitrile is a solvent commonly used for functionalization, we tried to increase the viscosity of the solution to increase the drag. We tested ACN:glycerol 2:1 v/v mixtures without obvious improvements. We also tested water, which gave an adequate drag for the material, but we discarded it due to the risk of hydrolysis and condensation reactions between the APTES molecules in parallel to the reaction on the surface of UVM-7. Finally, we evaluated the possibility of using DMSO, which although offered good transport of material and functionalizations around $18.0 \pm 0.5\%$ by mass, was discarded due to the difficulty of working with this type of solvent in large-scale productions. Therefore, we decided to keep acetonitrile as a solvent and focus on modifying the system. Among these adaptations we can highlight achieve a tube of adequate inner diameter, small enough to drive the solution homogeneously, but large enough to avoid blocking the conduction by the material and a configuration in which the tube was always advancing in favour of gravity. We opted for a rubber with an internal diameter of 6 mm. The organic load stands at $13.2 \pm 1.4\%$ (equivalent to $3.1 \text{ mmol APTES (g of silica)}^{-1}$). The measurements of nitrogen adsorption / desorption, show the expected reduction in the total area due to the blockage of the pores by APTES. The variation between in the total area between the fractions is higher in the flow functionalization in comparison with the flow synthesis, that could be assigned to the heterogeneous

character of the reaction and possible variations in the residence time of the material. Continuous microwave-assisted functionalization allows the obtention of 59 g of functionalized material in one hour.

Life Cycle Assessment and reduction of the environmental impact

The life cycle analysis (LCA) is a methodology that allows the identification of those processes that have the greatest environmental impact. It covers not only global warming, but many other parameters of great importance for the sustainability of human actions. Although at first glance it may seem that one process is more sustainable than another, this methodology allows us to quantify it and identify those reagents or processes with the greatest impact to try to reduce it.

In our case, the LCA has been applied to the four scaled up processes, the non-scaled synthesis and functionalization, and the conventional synthesis. The objective is to determine if, through the application of microwaves and scaling, in addition to a reduction in time, there is a variation in the environmental impact of the synthesis and functionalization of UVM-7. The system boundaries have been defined as a cradle-to-gate system. The use and disposal of the material have been left out of the study, as well as the emissions. The functional unit has been defined as the preparation of 1 kg of calcined UVM-7 or the functionalization of 1 kg of UVM-7. Life Cycle Inventories can be found in the Table 2. For a better data analysis, energy and solvents have been broken down into the different stages of the process and/or functions.

The main results of the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) have been collected in the figures 3 to 5. First, we considered the sum of the normalized impact values to identify which categories

Table 2. Life Cycle Inventory for the production or functionalization of 1 kg of UVM-7

Inventory	Reagents (Kg) or energy (KWh)			
	MW escalated batch	MW escalated flow	MW non-escalated	Conventional
TEOS	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,7
TEAH	8,4	8,4	8,4	9,2
CTABr	1,3	1,3	1,3	1,6
DIW synthesis	28,6	28,6	28,6	28,5
DIW washing	71,4	71,4	428,6	177,9
Ethanol washing	2,9	2,9	57,1	8,9
APTES	1,3	1,3	1,3	2,2
Acetonitrile functionaliz.	47,2	47,2	235,8	23,6
Acetonitrile washing	15,7	7,9	157,2	23,6
Energy synthesis	3,5	3,5	22,9	201,4
Energy calcination	360,5	360,5	970,0	1924,0
Energy functionaliz.	24,0	18,0	200,0	55,0

Figure 3: a) Normalized impact organized by synthesis method and impact category: global warming (GWP), stratospheric ozone depletion (SOP), ionizing radiation (IRP), ozone formation (human health) (OFH), fine particulate matter formation (PMFP), ozone formation (terrestrial ecosystems) (OFT), terrestrial acidification (TAC), freshwater eutrophication (FEU), marine eutrophication (MEU), terrestrial ecotoxicity (TEC), freshwater ecotoxicity (FEC), marine ecotoxicity (MEC), human carcinogenic toxicity (HCT), human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT), land use (LU), mineral resource scarcity (MRE), fossil resource scarcity (FRE) and water consumption (WC). b) Emission of CO₂ eq.

generated the greatest impact (see Figure 3.a). Unlike other studies where the contribution to global warming is highlighted, in our case the greatest impacts are in the categories of freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, and human carcinogenic toxicity and that these are largely dependent on the type of synthesis process. Also, the Global Warming Potential has been calculated and displayed in the Figure 3.b. The scaled synthesis developed in this work supposes a 5-fold reduction in the Kg of CO₂ eq generated per Kg of material with respect to the non-scaled synthesis and up to half compared to conventional synthesis.

We can use the single score calculated from the Endpoint analysis to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that influence the overall impact. To facilitate the analysis, we have divided the synthesis into the preparation of the "as-made" material, that has the surfactant inside the pores, and the calcination. If we review the influence of the different stages of

preparation of the functionalized UVM-7 (see Figure 4.a), we can observe that the different steps have a diverse level of impact and that this largely depends on the process type. Once again, it can be seen how the scaled processes have a much lower impact than the conventional or non-scaled and similar between them. Regarding the steps, the preparation of the material "as made" has in all cases a lower impact than the calcination and functionalization phases. The functionalization is especially important in the case of the non-scaled process. A better understanding of these results can be deduced from the impact of the different elements of the inventory (see Figure 4.b). The two main elements contributing to the impact are the use of acetonitrile in the functionalization and the electricity used in the calcination, accounting for between 85 and 91% of the impact depending on the type of process.

The cost of synthesis was estimated based in the LCI data and our unitary costs (see Supplementary material, Table S1 and S2).

Figure 4: a) Single score organized by synthesis method [conventional (conv), non scaled-up MW assisted synthesis (non sca.), scaled-up MW assisted batch synthesis (sca. batch), and scaled-up MW assisted flow synthesis (sca. flow)] and step of reaction; b) Single score organized by synthesis method and item of the inventory.

Figure 5: Single score for each scenario and synthesis step.

Although, the cost can be overestimated due to the use of laboratory cost data it can be useful to compare the four synthesis methods and identify opportunities of saving. The scaled-up processes offer a reduction of cost from almost 36 €/g to approximately 7.5 €/g, a 5-fold reduction. The most expensive step is the functionalization, due to the use of acetonitrile. Next, the second source of cost is the acquisition of reagents. By contrast, the energy cost is relatively low. If we compare the scaled processes with the conventional one, the main reduction is due to the reduction in the consumption of electricity.

From the LCA results and cost analysis we can conclude that the next steps to improve the scaled synthesis should be focused on reducing acetonitrile consumption and the impact of energy use. To reduce the consumption of acetonitrile, we can vary the solvent, but a more sustainable option may be to recover the solvent by distillation, using it in successive syntheses. Accordingly, we have proposed a scenario, in which the energy cost increases due to distillation and 95% of the acetonitrile can be recovered in each cycle. To reduce the impact of energy consumption in calcination, one option is to use electricity from renewable sources such as photovoltaics. Finally, we have proposed a scenario in which the previous two are combined. The results of the scenarios applied to scaled-up flow synthesis, the one with the lower impact, can be seen in Figure 5. The use of renewable energy in calcination almost avoids any impact in this phase, while distillation reduces the impact of functionalization by 9 times. When we combine both strategies, the sum of the single score drops from a score of 15.3 to just 3.7. Regarding the cost, savings higher than 60% could be obtained.

Experimental

Chemicals

All the synthesis reagents were analytically pure and were used without further purification. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), triethanolamine (TEAH3), cetyl-trimethylammonium bromide (CTABr), and (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) were

purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Acetonitrile and ethanol were purchased from Scharlab S.L.

Microwave devices

Two different solid-state (SS) device, one for batch processes and the other for flow processes were used. Both devices were provided by Microbiotech S.L. The batch device consists of four microwave sources connected through a coaxial cable to the irradiation cavity. Each source operates at a maximum power of 200 W selectable in 1 W increments, rising a maximum power of 800 W in total. The frequency of each source can be adjusted independently to tune the system and optimise the absorbed power within the 2420 MHz to 2480 MHz range in 1 Hz increments. The flow device consists of a SS microwave source with characteristics similar the batch device (maximum power of 200 W) but with selectable potency in 5 W increments.

Microwave assisted synthesis of UVM-7

ESCALATED BATCH SYNTHESIS

The synthesis of UVM7 is based in a previously reported method for UVM-7 preparation following the atrane route in combination with microwave irradiation.⁸ 1L deionized water was added to 412 mL of atrane mixture containing Si:TEAH3:CTABr in a 1:3.4:0.25 mole ratio (263 mL of TEAH3, 137 mL of TEOS, and 45 g of CTABr). The mixture was smoothly shaken until homogeneity, and then was placed into the microwave oven cavity and irradiated for 12 minutes at 800 W until the gel is formed. As a result, a white solid was obtained. This solid was isolated by filtration, washed with water and ethanol, dried in an oven at 80 °C overnight and calcined at 550 °C under static air atmosphere, as an oxidant atmosphere, for 5 h to remove the CTABr surfactant. The resulting material has been noted as BS800 (Batch Synthesis at 800 W). Samples collected at the centre and the side of the reactor have been noted as BS800c and BS800s respectively. Also, a batch of material irradiated at 400W for 25 minutes (BS400) and UVM-7 prepared with the conventional method in absence of MW, were synthesized for comparative purposes.⁵

ESCALATED BATCH FUNCTIONALIZATION

For the microwave assisted functionalization 2,5 g of calcined UVM-7 were dispersed in 150 mL of an APTES (15 mmol) solution in acetonitrile. The mixture was shaken for 10 seconds, and then placed into the microwave oven cavity. The suspension was irradiated for 4 to 16 minutes at 200W. After irradiation, the white solid is collected by filtration, washed with acetonitrile, and dried in an oven at 40 °C overnight. The resulting material was noted as BF-minutes (Batch Functionalization). The conventional procedure was also carried out as reference.⁶ The mixture of UVM-7, APTES and acetonitrile was stirred for 5.5 hours at room temperature. The solid was isolated, washed and dried as describe above.

FLOW SYNTHESIS OF UVM-7

The flow synthesis of UVM-7 is also based in a reported method for UVM-7 preparation following the atrane route.⁵ The atrane mixture was prepared as described above in the batch synthesis. The reagents, atrane and water, were pushed through the microwave system using two peristaltic pumps, one

for each reagent. The pumping rates were fixed at 10 rpm for the water and 5 rpm for the atrane to ensure a proper atrane: water ratio (0.41:1 v/v), and an irradiation time (remaining time inside the cavity) of 1 min. The microwave potency was set at 100 W. The product generated during the first minute was rejected and fractions were collected each 5 minutes. All the fractions were filtered, washed with water and ethanol, dried at 80 °C in an oven overnight, and calcined at 550 °C under static air atmosphere, as an oxidant atmosphere, for 5 h to remove the CTABr surfactant. The fractions were noted as FS-1 to FS-4 (Flow Synthesis).

FLOW FUNCTIONALIZATION

A 300 mL acetonitrile suspension containing 5 g of UVM-7 and 30 mmol of APTES under stirring was pumped through the microwave using a peristaltic pump. The pump speed was adjusted to 10 or 20 rpm (depending on the diameter of the conduction) to ensure a remaining time of 1 minute inside the cavity. The amount of material released was weighed at diverse times to ensure a continuous flux. The white solid was collected by filtration, washed with acetonitrile, and dried in an oven at 40 °C overnight. The resulting material was noted as FF (Flow Functionalization). During the optimization it was evaluated the effect of the solvent and the diameter of the conduction to ensure that the material moved uniformly through the system.

Characterization of the materials

All solids were characterized by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) at low angles (Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer) using a monochromatic Cu K α source operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. Patterns were collected in steps of 0.04° (2 θ) over the angular range 1.3–8.3° (2 θ) for 1 s per step. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were taken with a JEOL-JEM-1010 instrument operated at 100 kV (equipped with digital camera MegaView III and “ANALYSIS” software). Samples were gently ground in ethanol, and grains were deposited on a holey carbon film supported on a Cu grid. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms (-196 °C) were recorded on a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 automated analyser. The samples were degassed in situ at 120 °C and 10⁻⁶ Torr for 15 h prior to analysis. Specific surface areas were calculated from the adsorption data within the low-pressure range using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) model. Pore sizes and pore volumes were determined following the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) model on the adsorption branch. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were obtained with a SETARAM SETSYS 16–18 instrument (Caluire-et-Cuire, France) under a dry air flow at heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ up to 1000 °C.

Life Cycle Analysis

Life Cycle Analysis (ISO 14040:2006) in a cradle to gate basis was applied to the scaled processes. This technique allows the identification of the environmental impact of the processes and determine opportunities to improve their sustainability. The inventory was defined using the synthesis procedures and the energy consumption measured in the laboratory. The impact was calculated using the Ecoinvent 3 database and the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) V1.08 / World (2010) H/A model available in the SimaPro software. If available data from Spain or Europe

have been used. The method includes as impact categories global warming, stratospheric ozone depletion, ionizing radiation, ozone formation (human health), fine particulate matter formation, ozone formation (terrestrial ecosystems), terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, terrestrial ecotoxicity, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, human carcinogenic toxicity, human non-carcinogenic toxicity, land use, mineral resource scarcity, fossil resource scarcity and water consumption. CTABr and APTES are not available in the data base, thus, estequat (a cationic surfactant) and TEOS (a silane) were used for the analysis.

Conclusions

We have reported for the first time a scaled-up batch microwave assisted synthesis of UVM-7, a silica mesoporous material in batch. Also, we have described the first, up to our knowledge, flow microwave assisted synthesis of a silica mesoporous material. The materials obtained following the batch and flow scaled procedures have structure and properties similar to the material prepared under conventional conditions. As made material for the preparation of 168 and 59 g of calcined material per hour can be obtained with the batch and flow methods respectively. The functionalization of UVM-7 can be performed in less than 5 minutes with loadings of organic groups of 3.2 mmol of APTES (g of silica)⁻¹. Up to 59 g of UVM-7 h⁻¹ can be functionalized. LCA shows that the scaled-up synthesis offers a strong reduction in the environmental impact, but it could be further reduced by the reutilization of solvents and the use of renewable energy.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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